

COMPARATIVE ANALYZES OF AFFIXATION IN UZBEK AND
ENGLISH

A'zamjonova Azimaxon

Fergana state university,

English language and literature faculty,

Department of English language teaching methodology, teacher

Karimova Kamola Rustam qizi

Fergana state university,

English language and literature faculty,

Department of English language teaching methodology, teacher

kamolasultonova3002@gmail.com

ANNOTATSIYA

O'zbek tilining milliy madaniy xususiyatlari nafaqat so'z, maqola, hikoya, maqol, aforizmlarda, balki kognitiv tilshunoslikda muhim rol o'ynaydigan o'zbek tilining ayrim affikslarida ham uchraydi. Ular har bir xalqning milliy urf-odatlarini, madaniyati, milliy xarakterining aksi sifatida qaraladi. Ushbu maqola o'zbek tilidagi kognitiv lingvistika nuqtai nazaridan affikslarning semantik ma'nolarini o'rganishga va sayohatchilarning madaniy turizmga aks etishiga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Kontrastiv tahlil, ingliz tili, o'zbek tili.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Национально-культурные особенности узбекского языка проявляются не только в словах, статьях, рассказах, пословицах, афоризмах, но и в некоторых аффиксах узбекского языка, которые играют важную роль в когнитивной лингвистике. Они рассматриваются как отражение национальных традиций, культуры и национального характера каждого народа. Данная статья посвящена изучению семантических значений

аффиксов с точки зрения когнитивной лингвистики в узбекском языке и в рефлексии путешественников в культурном туризме.

Ключевые слова: контрастивный анализ, английский, узбекский язык.

ANNOTATION

The national cultural features of the Uzbek language not only occur in words, articles, stories, proverbs, aphorisms but also in some affixes of the Uzbek language that play vital role in cognitive linguistics. They are considered as reflection of national traditions, culture, and national character of every nation. This article is devoted to the investigation of semantic meanings of affixes from point of view cognitive linguistics in Uzbek language and in reflection the travelers in cultural tourism.

Keywords: Contrastive Analysis, English, Uzbek Language.

Meaning of affixation in English the process of adding an affix (= a letter or group of letters with a particular meaning added to the beginning or end of a word to make a new word), or a letter or group of letters that are added like this: Languages differ in their use of affixation.

There are three main types of affixes: prefixes, infixes, and suffixes. A prefix occurs at the beginning of a word or stem (sub-mit, pre-determine, un-willing); a suffix at the end (wonder-ful, depend-ent, act-ion); and an infix occurs in the middle.

Affixes have two main purposes: grammar and simplifying communication. First, affixes are used in English grammar: they make a word singular or plural, create new verb tenses, and change the word class of a word. For example, you can add an –s or –es to the end of most nouns to make them plural.

Affixation is a morphological process whereby a bound morpheme, an affix, is attached to a morphological base. Diachronically, the English word affix was first used as a verb and has its origin in Latin: affixes, past participle of the verb affixer, ad- 'to' + figure 'to fix'.

There are three types of affixes: prefixes, suffixes, and circumfixes. Let's take a closer look at these now. Fig.

Another productive process is affixation, where a derivational suffix or prefix is attached to a word or a bound morpheme. Neologisms often use relatively unproductive affixes. Recent examples include girdom, astronauts, marketeer, bemeaned, retribalize, and circumstellar.

Linguistics is one of the modern trends in linguistics, which reflects language and culture interactions. Nowadays knowledge of foreign language and its comprehensive study are becoming a popular demand. It is well known that each person belongs to a specific culture, including national traditions, language, history, literature. Which has led to the interpretation of the language as a means of expression of the cultural value of the economic, cultural and scientific relations between the two countries. E. Sopher emphasizes that, "Language is a means of learning a culture." Learning a language is not only a matter of learning words, not just talk, but about the culture of the country studied, the way of life and tradition. Which in its turn led to the emergence of a new field of linguistics, linguistic sciences.

The objective of linguistics is to study linguistic and cultural relations, to reflect the culture of language, to learn intercultural dialogue. The main concept of linguistics is linguoculturism. Lingoculteremas include words expression a certain part of culture (synonyms, common and complex words), and phraseological units, vocabularies, paraments, folklore texts and so on. Including some affixes, which are among the language units mentioned above. In these units, the national cultural features of that nation are evident. Different uses of units expressing the context of positive wishes by age and gender are observed.

The combination of the gourmet shaped shape is mainly used by adults in the Uzbek language. You will be rich, your children will be plentiful, your wealth will be full of wealth, your wealth will be long, your head will be as an example.

Positive affirmative desire units, as well as women's speeches. Typically, the use of grunge-shaped irregular shapes is specific to a woman's speech, with a positive desire to do so; basharang qurmag`ur, qurib ketmagur kabi. This means that the meaning of a negative desire in different devices is weakened and the content is expressed; Ey qurib ketmagur, nega indamading shu vaqtgacha? Basharang qurmag`ur tezroq keta qolmaysanmi(U.Hoshimov)

In the speech of the women, the speeches in which the positive wishes are expressed are colorful they are also given in the forms of the -(a)y,-sin; "Aylanay, bo`ylaringga qoqindiq, sadag`ang ketay, onaginang aylansin, bo`yingdan o`rgilay" such units are mainly used in the speech of woman; -Xush kelibsiz-dedi Oftob oyim... -Xushvaqt bo`linglar, aylanay,-dedi xotin(A.Qodiriy)

The national cultural features of the Uzbek language not only occur in words, articles, stories, aphorisms but also in some affixes of the Uzbek language. The peculiarity of the affixes such as -gur, -ay, -sin in the Uzbek language is characteristics of the Uzbek people, which is often characterized by literary art. That it belongs to a representative of that nation.

It might motivate travelers to learn the local language in order to prepare them better for their future travel experiences and they might be able to be aware of our enrichens and the national spirit of Uzbek language. Many languages contain words that are morphologically related, learning one base word might increase the total vocabulary. Therefore, learning inflectional suffixes helps us to put together sentences and understand the language of others.

The national cultural features of the Uzbek language not only occur in words, articles, stories, aphorisms but also in some affixes of the Uzbek language. The peculiarity of the affixes such as -gur, -ay, -sin in the Uzbek language is characteristics of the Uzbek people, which is often characterized by literary art. That it belongs to a representative of that nation. It might motivate travelers to learn the local language in order to prepare them better for their future travel

experiences and they might be able to be aware of our enrichens and the national spirit of Uzbek language. Many languages contain words that are morphologically related, learning one base word might increase the total vocabulary.

REFERENCES

1. William O'Grady, J. Archibald, M. Aronoff, and J. Rees-Miller, "Contemporary Linguistics: An Introduction". Bedford/St. Martin's, 2001.
2. Hojiev A. "O'zbek tili so'z yasaliş tizimi". T. 1989 y.
3. Hojiev A. "O'zbek tili morfologiyasi, morfemikasi va so'z yasalişining nazariy masalalari". T. 1989 y.
4. "O'zbek tilining asosiy imlo qoidalari". Toshkent, 1995 y.
5. Arnold I.V. "The English word"- 1986
6. Ginzgurg "A course of modern English lexicology". L.1979
7. Hatcher A.G. "An introduction to the analysis of English noun compounds". L. 1960